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Lecturers' Perceived Challenges towards the Efficient Use of Digital Technologies for Effective Teaching of Agricultural Education in the University in South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this study was to examine lecturers' perceived challenges towards the efficient use of digital technologies for Effective Teaching of Agricultural Education in the Universities in South-South Nigeria. One research questions was raised and answered. The research instrument for the study was the questionnaire named "lecturers' perceived challenges towards the efficient use of digital technologies for Effective Teaching of Agricultural Education in the Universities in South-south Nigeria" (LPCEUDTETAEUSSN). The reliability of the instrument was established using test – retest reliability method which was used to ensure the reliability of instrument, a reliability coefficient index of 0.70 was established which indicated that the instrument was highly reliable. Frequency Count, Means (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answer the research question. Arising from the analysis of data, the following result/finding showed that there numerous challenges confronting lecturers towards the use of digital technologies such as: insufficient or outdated hardware, software and poor internet connectivity, Staff and students lack skills to use digital technology, High cost of data, Lack of digital resources availability among others. Based on the finding recommendation was made: Regular training for the Lecturers particularly to catch up with the needed skills to operate the equipment is also recommended. Joint venture efforts with universities faculties of engineering to fabricate some of the hardware should be encouraged based on research efforts and results.

Keywords: Agricultural Education, Challenges, Lecturers, Digital Technologies

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural Education is a field of study that prepares individuals for career in aspects of food and agricultural system. Ekong and Paul (2020) described Agricultural Education as a programme that is geared towards preparing people for skilled work, stipulating the training and retraining of the individuals to enable them acquire specific appreciation of the patterns of behaviour, attitudes, skills, knowledge, values and culture needed to become more productive and efficient in the society. Ebusoh (2010) depicted that Agricultural Education is basically undertaken to prepare students for employment in the agriculture and education sectors. Agricultural Education in this study implies a field of study in Universities in South-South Nigeria that trains an individual to acquire knowledge, skills and attitude in agriculture. In the universities, lecturers of Agricultural Education train their students to be competent and graduate them

to be teachers of Agriculture in Junior and Senior Secondary schools, Colleges as well as Universities. In the quest for improving teaching and learning process and solving educational problems, educational researchers came up with e-teaching (Digital technologies teaching)

In spite of the immense benefits derivable from the use of digital technologies devices, a number of challenges still militate against their use in improving the teaching and learning process generally in Nigerian Universities. According to Ogunbodede et al, (2023) Universities in the South-South geopolitical zone—comprising AkwaIbom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers States have invested, to varying degrees, in learning management systems (LMS), computer laboratories, e-libraries, smart classrooms and multimedia tools; yet the pace and depth of classroom integration often depend on lecturers' perceptions of the usefulness, ease, and relevance of these tools to agricultural content and field-based instruction. University Lecturers are pivotal because they select tools, design learning activities, and model technology use for pre-service agricultural teachers and other student cohorts. However, their perceived challenges shape day-to-day adoption decisions. These challenges can be understood across four interrelated domains—technological, organisational, pedagogical, and individual (UNESCO, 2014). It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate on lecturers' perceived challenges towards the efficient use of digital technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in the University South-South Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Improving teaching and learning outcomes through the use of digital technologies in the classroom has become a global focus. Digital technologies offer prospects for improved instructional delivery and higher learner engagement in Agriculture Education, where access to contemporary agricultural information, simulation, and practical demonstration are essential. The degree to which South-South Nigerian professors successfully use ICTs for instruction is still debatable, despite institutional and governmental investments in this infrastructure.

According to studies, lecturers frequently encounter several obstacles while implementing digital tools, such as insufficient training, unreliable internet connectivity, epileptic power supplies, lack of institutional support, and little exposure to new technologies. Traditional teaching methods are still widely used by Agricultural Education Lecturers/instructors in many South-South universities, which may not sufficiently prepare students for the demands of the contemporary agricultural economy. This circumstance raises questions about how well Agricultural Education prepares graduates for the skills of the twenty-first century by separating policy intentions from classroom practice. Students may continue to graduate with inadequate digital skills if these issues continue, which would undermine national initiatives for sustainable development, food security, and agricultural modernization. It is against this backdrop that an investigation into lecturers' perceived challenges towards the efficient use of digital technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in the university in South-South Nigeria becomes necessary.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine lecturers' perceived challenges towards the efficient use of digital technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in the University in South-South Nigeria.

Research Question

The study was guided by this research question:

What are Lecturers' Perceived Challenges towards the efficient use of Digital Technologies for Effective Teaching of Agricultural Education in the University in South-South Nigeria?

The Challenges Facing the Use of Digital Technologies

Many researchers identified challenges to the efficacious integration of Digital technologies in the teaching and learning process. These challenges include but are not limited to poor internet connectivity, poor installation, inadequate professional development, poor support and leadership (Ertmer, 2019). A study on the contribution of the Information and Communication Technology on service delivery in schools in Tanzania, the study revealed that irregular power supply, high cost in purchasing computers

and lack of funds are the major challenges facing the application of digital technologies in school (Metu et al., 2022). Therefore, in order to integrate effectively, there must be good infrastructure such as software devices, hardware devices and internet access. Many teachers in schools do not have sufficient knowledge and skills on the use of digital technologies in teaching and learning. Other factors are related to teachers' beliefs in terms of deficiency of digital technologies physical activity and application, insufficient technical support, lack of cooperation and peer technological support, slow connectivity and power disappointment, lack of confidence in applying modern technologies in teaching duties or the like (Papoioannon & Charalambous, 2019).

Ertmer (2019) classified these challenges into first and second order categories. First-order challenges relate to hardware and software designs, while second-order challenges relate to internal issues such as learners' motivation as well as the supervision level of learners' activities. There are many challenges centre on accessibility and infrastructure which affect teaching and learning using technologies (Metu et al., 2022). As suggested by United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (2014), effective digital technologies in education policies depend on three main pillars, namely access to digital technologies infrastructure and equipment, teachers' capacities and monitoring. Indeed, satisfactory realisation of these pillars is still facing significant challenges. OECD (2015) pointed out some major challenges that are likely to be encountered in the implementation of the above presented policy including inadequate infrastructure, electricity coverage in public schools, low internet connectivity rate, lack of equipment and high costs, limited access to digital technologies in the education system (computer to students ratio in secondary schools is 40:1, while 16% of primary schools have access to laptops thanks to the One Laptop Per Child project). Correspondingly, the limited availability of digital learning materials, lack of expertise in project management and poor coordination of existing initiatives, technical support were also the challenge. Elsewhere, factors impeding the effectiveness of digital technologies integration in teaching and learning are related with students' lack of digital technologies skills.

However, Ike-Obioha and Ikwuegbe (2015); Shehwar and Fenta (2023) reported that the problems of digital technologies in education include, but not limited to the following:

1. There is dearth of qualified staff in ICT as well as infrastructural facilities that impedes the smooth usage of the technology.
2. The cost of most of the digital technologies gadgets especially software is highly prohibitive and with the present socio-economic background of teachers. The cost of computers is too high for many to afford. Monthly internet rates are exorbitant and the charges for satellite television are unaffordable by most people in Africa. The urge to procure these soft wares may be a nightmare. This has made it difficult for Nigerian secondary schools and some higher institutions of learning to acquire and install digital technologies facilities for use by teachers and students.
3. Illiteracy: Most of the teachers are illiterate in the use of digital technologies and may not be interested in adopting it.
4. Poor information infrastructure. It has been reported that more than 40 percent of the population of Africa is in areas not covered by telecommunication services. Schools located in such areas will experience digital technologies connectivity problem.
5. Lack of/inadequate digital technologies facilities in schools in Nigeria. Electricity failure has been a persistent problem militating against digital technologies application and use in Nigeria. This makes the few schools with digital technologies facilities unable to use them regularly.
6. Poor digital technologies policy implementation strategy: The Federal Republic of Nigeria policy introduced computer education to high schools. The only policy implemented was the distribution of computers to federal government high schools which were never used for computer education of the students. No effort was made to distribute computer to state government or private schools. So, most schools do not yet offer digital technologies training programmes.
7. Inadequate digital technologies manpower in the schools: The main problem facing Nigeria and its digital technologies programme is workforce training. Teaching as a profession in Nigeria is considered to be for poor people; therefore the few professionals that are available prefer to work in

companies and industries where they can earn better salaries. With this deplorable condition, teachers are not motivated to go the extra mile in assisting the students to acquire computer education. Abba and Lamido - Gora (2019) found out that the level of university lecturers' proficiency and usefulness of digital and internet facilities are major factors that encouraged them to frequently access electronic resources for dissemination of academic finding via publication.

8. Poor perception of digital technologies among teachers and administrators: There is a widespread ignorance and misconception about digital technologies amongst Nigerians. One of the major inhibitors to Nigeria fully embracing digital technologies is the average Nigerian's general lack of exposure to them. For most Nigerians, information technology is still something unfamiliar, distant, and mysterious. Rather than being seen as a tool for personal and national development, information technology is seen as a hurdle. E-schools project have no or very limited experience and expertise regarding digital technologies in education.

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for this study was the ex-post-facto design. 929 lecturers of Agricultural Education and Faculty of Agriculture was the population for this study. 279 lecturers were drawn from the universities located in South-south Nigeria and this number of lecturers served as the sample for the study. This sample size was computed using the Taro Yamane formula at 95% level of confidence. The research instrument for the study was the questionnaire named "lecturers' perceived challenges towards the efficient use of digital technologies for Effective Teaching of Agricultural Education in the Universities in South-south Nigeria" (LPCEUDTETAEUSSN). The reliability of the instrument was established using test – retest reliability method which was used to ensure the reliability of instrument, a reliability coefficient index of 0.70 was established which indicated that the instrument was highly reliable. Frequency Count, Means (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answer the research question.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question One: *What are Lecturers' Perceived Challenges towards efficient use of Digital Technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in the Universities in South-South Nigeria?*

Table 1: *Mean score and standard deviation on lecturers' perceived challenges towards efficient use of Digital Technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in the Universities in South-South Nigeria*

S/N	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Decision
1	Infrastructures such as insufficient or outdated hardware, software and poor internet connectivity.	3.50	0.50	Agree
2	Staff and students lack skills to use digital technology.	4.00	0.00	Agree
3	High cost of data.	3.50	0.50	Agree
4	Lack of digital resources availability.	4.00	0.00	Agree
5	Lack of protection against cyber threats, data breaches and privacy concerns.	3.50	0.50	Agree
6	Lack of integration of digital technology into existing curriculum and pedagogy	4.00	0.00	Agree
7	Lack of adequate technical support and training for lecturers.	3.50	0.50	Agree
8	Lack of equal access to digital tools.	3.50	0.50	Agree
9	Digital distractions.	4.00	0.00	Agree
10	Ethical issue such as online plagiarism.	3.50	0.50	Agree
11	Conservatism to the adoption of new digital technology by some lecturers.	3.00	0.00	Agree
12	Lack of Digital Skills among Lecturers	4.00	0.00	Agree
13	Issue of gender.	1.50	0.50	Disagree
14	Lack of Power (electricity) issue such as source, irregularity etc.	4.00	0.00	Agree
15	High cost of Digital Resources.	4.00	0.00	Agree
Aggregate mean		3.57	0.23	Agree

Table 1 shows the mean score and standard deviation on *lecturers' perceived challenges towards efficient use of digital technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in universities in South-south Nigeria*. According to the result, respondents agree on all the items with the exception of item13 which has mean score below 2.50. Respondents agree on all the items with mean scores of 3.50, 4.00, 3.50, 4.00, 3.50, 4.00, 3.50, 3.50, 4.00, 3.50, 3.00, 4.00, 1.50, 4.00and 4.00. With regards to the responses, it could be concluded that *lecturers' perceived challenge towards efficient use of digital technologies for effective teaching of Agricultural Education in universities in South-south Nigeria* include; Infrastructures such as insufficient or outdated hardware, software and poor internet connectivity, Staff and students lack skills to use digital technology, High cost of data, Lack of digital resources availability, Lack of protection against cyber threats, data breaches and privacy concerns, Lack of integration of digital technology into existing curriculum and pedagogy, Lack of adequate technical support and training for lecturers, Lack of equal access to digital tools, Digital distractions, Ethical issue such as online plagiarism, Conservatism to the adoption of new digital technology by some lecturers, Lack of Digital Skills among Lecturers, Lack of Power (electricity) issue such as source, irregularity etc. and High cost of Digital Resources.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study on Table 1 revealed the view of Agricultural Education Lecturers on the challenges facing them in the use of digital technologies for effective teaching of Agriculture in South-South Universities of Nigeria to include: Infrastructures such as insufficient or outdated hardware, software and poor internet connectivity, Staff and students lack skills to use digital technology, High cost of data, Lack of digital resources availability, Lack of protection against cyber threats, data breaches and privacy concerns, Lack of integration of digital technology into existing curriculum and pedagogy, Lack of adequate technical support and training for lecturers, Lack of equal access to digital tools, Digital distractions, Ethical issue such as online plagiarism, Conservatism to the adoption of new digital technology by some lecturers, Lack of Digital Skills among Lecturers, Lack of Power (electricity) issue such as source, irregularity among others and High cost of Digital Resources.

CONCLUSION

Although digital tools have enormous potential to revolutionize agricultural instruction, their adoption is hampered by a number of factors, according to a study on lecturers' perceived barriers to using them effectively for teaching agricultural education in South-South Nigeria. Inadequate infrastructure, erratic electrical supplies, poor internet access, a lack of institutional support, and certain professors' lacking digital competency are important examples of these. These difficulties not only make it more difficult to incorporate cutting-edge technology into instruction, but they also lessen the efficiency of agricultural education in providing students with the pertinent knowledge and abilities required in the technologically advanced agricultural industry of today.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Regular training for the Lecturers particularly to catch up with the needed skills to operate the equipment is recommended.
2. Joint venture efforts with universities faculties of engineering to fabricate some of the hardware should be encouraged based on research efforts and results.
3. Government policy on digital use in schools should be practically implemented so as to overcome most of the highlighted challenges.

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